

COMPETENCY APPROACH OF PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS OF STUDENTS IN
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Abstract. In the following article, it is stated that the formation of pedagogical skills in students is an urgent socio-pedagogical problem, the concepts of "pedagogical skills", "competence", their composition, various approaches to these concepts, the role of competence and competence in personal development. described. The approaches of many pedagogues and psychologists have been analyzed. As a result of these analyses, scientific opinions are stated.

Keywords: learner, skill, competence, competence, personal development, ducational process, knowledge, skill, competence, basic life competence, science competence. competence, competence, personal development, educational process, knowledge, skills, competence, basic life competence, scientific competence.

Аннотация. В следующей статье констатируется, что формирование педагогических умений у студентов является актуальной социально-педагогической проблемой, рассматриваются понятия «педагогическое мастерство», «компетентность», их состав, различные подходы к этим понятиям, роль компетентности и компетентности. описана компетентность в личном развитии. Проанализированы подходы многих педагогов и психологов. В результате этих анализов формулируются научные мнения.

Ключевые слова: учащийся, умение, компетентность, компетенция, личностное развитие, образовательный процесс, знания, умение, компетентность, базовая жизненная компетентность, научная компетентность.

Modern conditions require every member of society, especially the young generation, to master digital competence at a perfect level. The main reason for this is the rapid development of digital techniques and technologies in the process of globalization, as a result of which the Internet, various social networks, and the flow of information and data are increasing.

It is possible to change people's mind and ideology through information. It is becoming clear that it is possible to control people's worldview through information. The saying that the world is governed by information is becoming a reality. At a time when the ownership and delivery of information is becoming a requirement, the information space is expanding more and more. As a result of the increase in the types of information, the appearance of information is also radically changing. The Internet, which is used as a source of information, is full of various confirmed and unconfirmed information. It is in this situation that the formation of the culture of

receiving information and the ability to analyze it is important. For this, society needs to be informed.

What will an information society look like? Informatization of society is a situation that occurs as a result of the rapid development of information technologies in a certain country or society. In order for the society to be informed, first of all, it is necessary to develop information technologies in the society and meet the requirements. In an information society, the flow of information will be free. In addition to influencing the national ideology, this creates several moral threats. In the beginning of any armed wars there is an influence of the information process. The attack of information is the first step of wars. The relevance of ensuring information security today is determined by this situation. As humanity is entering a new era called "Information Society", ensuring information security is more important than ever. During the formation of the culture of information consumption, it is understood that people use knowledge and ability to collect information. In this process, information is divided into necessary and unnecessary types and analyzed. The process of receiving approved information will be accelerated. In a society without a culture of information consumption, various threats and unrest arise. Because information is power. It can be used for good or bad purposes.

The formation of students' ability to sort information is carried out by checking the facts of a multidisciplinary scientific journal. Here are some recommendations:

- ❖ Check when a user's page is opened on a social network.
- ❖ Explore user activity.
- ❖ Look for the user's pages on other social networks.
- ❖ Contact the person who downloaded and published the news.
- ❖ Compare what the user is talking to who you know
- ❖ Compare location information.
- ❖ Use reverse search by image
- ❖ Check photo EXIF data.

One of the urgent issues is the application of information technologies, which express the spirit of the times and are increasingly entering the practice of all fields, into the educational process of general education schools. The worldwide information network can provide any amount of information in any field, regardless of its volume and speed. The emergence of multimedia and Internet technologies opened a wide way for the use of information technologies as an effective tool in education and training, communication processes in general education schools. It cannot be denied that the role and influence of information technologies in the development of a well-rounded person, his independent choice of profession and professional self-formation, and the development of professional skills are increasing. In the educational

process in general education schools, the following opportunities are opened to teachers and students with the help of information technologies, in particular:

- ❖ □ learn new methods of information gathering and their application;
- ❖ □ children's thinking range expands, their interest in learning increases;
- ❖ □ the role of independent work increases, efficiency improves;
- ❖ □ to develop the child intellectually, to expand the emotional-aesthetic circle, positively
- ❖ □ helps to develop skills.

Using computers and information technologies, new opportunities are created in the field of education, in educational activities and in the development of students' creative thinking. Information technologies allow to combine education with life in the process of implementation. There will be an opportunity to closely connect education with future professional activity. In the application of information technologies, it is necessary to strive to realize all the possibilities of the student's personality: to realize the cognitive, moral, creative, communication and aesthetic possibilities and abilities of the child through computer tools. In order to turn computers and information technologies into a full-fledged tool for the development of the student's personality, the teacher himself must be knowledgeable (competent) in the field of information technologies.

Today, the participants of education (teacher, pupil, student) are surrounded by constant changes, the study habits of students have naturally changed, and their needs and conditions are not the same as ten years ago. Therefore, it is very important for educational institutions to pay attention to increasing media literacy of students and strengthening their ideological immunity to information that promotes foreign ideas. In a word, education should be didactic and safe, meeting the spiritual needs of the young generation. In order to achieve the intended goal, a teacher who takes over the educational process of students and helps them master basic skills, has updated professional training, professional competencies specific to pedagogues, as well as digital competence is required.

Only a teacher with high pedagogical skills, scientific potential, and at the same time possessing digital competence who can effectively and widely use ICT can meet the demands of today's times, who is competitive, proactive, aspiring, active, creative and critical thinker, able to meet world standards. can train suitable personnel. That is why it is of great importance for students of higher education institutions, especially future teachers, to be able to think critically in the development of professional skills and qualifications. Today, the organization of education based on the competency approach, the formation and regular development of the competencies of teachers and students are among the urgent issues of pedagogy.

Before thinking about the competence approach of digital competence and other

pedagogical skills, let's dwell on the meaning of this term.

Competence is a Latin word, which in Uzbek means "suitable", "suitable" or "suitable". He can be understood as a person capable of solving simple and complex problems using his knowledge, skills and practical experience.

Competence is a pre-set social requirement for educational preparation of students for effective activity in a certain field. Competence is multifaceted and has several interpretations. Competency refers to the acquisition of appropriate competencies by the learner. Competence includes the personal qualities of the student and the minimum level of knowledge, skills, skills and practical experience accumulated by the activity in the given field. Special competencies and basic competencies are mutually different. Basic competencies are a model of the student's life and social activity in the future. When students acquire certain knowledge, skills, qualifications and experience, they can apply the acquired competencies through their activities. Basic competencies are considered necessary for the future social activity of the student. Competencies mastered within the framework of a special educational subject mainly ensure the effectiveness of educational and professional activities in the future.

Competencies are formed based on the lifestyle, cultural, spiritual life and traditions of the people of each country. Competences formed in students are creative, i.e. creative, and encourage them to be active regularly. Such competencies include communicative, working with information, self-development, social-emotional and civic. Special attention should be paid to students' experience of using competencies. For this purpose, it is necessary to design curriculums, textbooks, instructional manuals based on the competency approach, to include educational materials and educational tasks that serve to create competencies in secondary projects chosen by teachers, and to develop digital didactic tools. From this point of view, the approach is gaining special relevance.

Based on the continuity of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan and its focus on educating a well-rounded person, basic competencies and Based on the content of each academic subject, subject-related competencies were determined. One of the important tasks facing the science of pedagogy is to clearly consider general and specific approaches to the formation of basic life competencies in elementary school students and to develop the theoretical and didactic foundations of this phenomenon based on existing methodological approaches.

In recent years, the concept of forming pedagogical skills of students in the digital educational environment has been widely used in pedagogy. This term, which is often used in educational practice, occupies a priority place in the content of education. Formation of pedagogical skills of students in the digital educational environment is undergoing the stages of absorption into the scientific concepts of modern pedagogy as a basic concept. The peculiarity

of this concept is that it requires mutual comparison with outdated concepts in the science of pedagogy.

In the course of our research, we try to explain the concepts that are included in the framework of the formation of pedagogical skills in students in the digital educational environment and are interconnected with it. They are: competence, competence, professional competence, formation of pedagogical skills. In addition, during our research, we tried to reflect on each of the pedagogical skills, competence and readiness, competence and knowledge, skills, and qualifications.

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